

PLAGIARISM DETECTION SOFTWARE: PERSPECTIVES FROM ACADEMIC STAFF

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Introduction

Plagiarism has become a major talking point when considering academic publishing today. Some have attributed the increased narrative on plagiarism to technology. The Internet is often referred to have caused a rapid increase of plagiarism issues as it makes it easy for individuals to search, retrieve, copy and paste from electronic sources. Yet technology itself has introduced the solution for this issue in the form of Plagiarism Detection Software. Although this category of software aims to eradicate plagiarism, it should be introduced in the academic context without breaking the values and processes of the academic agendas. “The academic institute should use the plagiarism detection software as a secondary instrument of defense rather than the primary instrument of defense.” (Thomas 2008)

The author’s exploration of this topic has revealed that even though there is increased discussion on the subject, there has been less research carried out. “Although plagiarism is a significant problem in universities and the tendency growing sky-high all over the world, very limited studies had been conducted in Sri Lanka relating to plagiarism” (Kodikara & Kumara 2015). Our study only found one research focusing on the Plagiarism Detection Software – Turnitin, and how it affected academic integrity and the honesty in a Sri Lankan University” (Ranawella 2018). This study, however, does not focus on the User’s Perspective on Plagiarism Detection Software. The perspective of the users of a system or software is a critical success factor for the usage of that software or the system. This is due to the fact that it would decide the rate of using certain software. After deriving the research problem, the research objective was formulated subsequently. The research objective was to “Examine the factors influencing the lecturer’s perspective of intention to use the plagiarism detection software”.

This study focused on Intention to use the Plagiarism Detection Software rather than the Actual Use. The reason behind this is, the focused population for this study had limited access to the software as a result the factor, Intention to Use the Software is encouraged for this study while promoting to use the software.

Methodology

This study was carried out as quantitative research. The population of this study included the Academic Staff of a Management Faculty of a State University in Sri Lanka which is about 250. The sample size was decided according to Morgan's table which is about 150 (with a 95% confidence rate and a 5% margin of error) and that covered all the academic departments in the faculty. Lecturers were selected randomly from the departments and distributed with the printed questionnaire. A seven-point Likert scaled questionnaire is formulated using two research papers which present the "Extension to Technology Acceptance Model" (Venkatesh & Davis 2000) (Venkatesh 2000) and questions were modified according to this study. For the data analysis purpose, Smart PLS and SPSS software were used.

Results and Discussion

In the research model of this study, five hypotheses were developed. Among these five, only one hypothesis was rejected after the inferential analysis. The rejected hypothesis was "The Output Quality has a positive influence on Perceived Usefulness". The effect of Output Quality on the Perceived Usefulness is not statistically significant with the p value of 0.082. The T- Statistics value is also below the 1.96 which is 1.74 and path coefficient also -0.140. Therefore, this hypothesis was rejected. This result contradicted with the previous results (Venkatesh & Davis 2000); it showed the path coefficient value of 0.40.

Moreover, when considering the Perceived Usefulness with the R^2 value of 0.155 it defines the variable Output Quality only influence 15.5% to Perceived Usefulness. There are 84.5% other variables affect the Perceived Usefulness. In this research, it only considered the Output Quality as the determinants of Perceived Usefulness. But according to (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000) there are other determinants as Subjective Norm, Image, Job Relevance, and Result

Demonstrability. Sometimes these variables may affect differently on the Perceived Usefulness. Apart from that Output Quality is the determinant influence for the actual use rather than the Intention to Use. Because the users of the software were concerned about the Output Quality after they use it, not before they use it. In this research model, Actual Use was not considered.

Conclusion

The findings of this study can be implicated to get an idea for the academic institutions where the plagiarism detection software is not yet introduced and can be implicated as a promotional material to promote the use of the plagiarism detection software in the academic context.

The Plagiarism Detection Software should not be used as the primary tool to eradicate plagiarism by relying on it. It is recommended to be used only as a supporting tool to eradicate plagiarism just as the people use computers for process data. Moreover, if the users of this software highly depend on it and are not concerned with other ways of eradicating plagiarism, the students and the other affected parties from this software may tend to search for a technical solution which can be used to mask from getting highlighted as a perpetrator of plagiarism. Since technology itself provides the momentum to promote unethical practices like plagiarism, technology itself provides the solution for plagiarism. Therefore finally, it is possible to produce a solution for masking from getting highlighted as a plagiarizer.

The fact that the study was limited to academic staff is a limitation of this study. Future researchers are encouraged to explore an environment where both students and the lecturers have access to the software factor in “Actual Usage”.

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